

The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy

By Lampros Alexopoulos, University of Thessaloniki

Entry tags: Religious Group, Christian Traditions, Orthodoxy, Heresy

On October 13, 787 the Second Council of Nicaea decreed that the venerable and Holy Icons are to be dedicated in the holy churches of God, namely the image of our Lord and God and Savior Jesus Christ, of our immaculate Lady the Holy Theotokos (Virgin Mary), and of the angels and all the saints. They are to be accorded the veneration of honor, not indeed the true worship paid to the divine nature alone, but in the same way, as this is accorded to the life-giving cross, the holy gospels, and other sacred offerings. Few years after that decree, Emperor Leo V the Armenian, a senior general who assumed the throne of the Byzantine Empire, after forcing his predecessor, Michael I Rangabe, to resign in 813, launched a second period of Iconoclasm in 815. Leo's motivations were perhaps the military failures, that were regarded as indicators of divine displeasure. The Byzantines had suffered a series of humiliating defeats at the hands of the Bulgarians, in the course of which emperor Nikephoros I (802-811) had been killed in battle and emperor Michael I Rangabe had been forced to abdicate. Soon after his accession, Leo V began to discuss the possibility of reviving iconoclasm with a variety of people, including priests, monks, and members of the senate, stating that any of the previous emperors, who embraced the veneration of the Holy Icons, met their death either in revolt or in war; but those who did not venerate images all died a natural death, remained in power until they died, and were then laid to rest with all honors in the imperial mausoleum in the Church of the Holy Apostles. His next move was to appoint a committee of monks to look into the old books and reach a decision on the veneration of the Holy Icons. They soon discovered the acts of the Iconoclastic Synod, summoned by the Emperor Constantine V in 754 in the palace of Hieria at Chalcedon. The council supported the emperor's iconoclast position in the Byzantine iconoclasm controversy, condemning the spiritual and liturgical use of iconography as heretical. A debate between Leo's supporters and the clergy who continued to advocate the veneration of the Holy Icons, led by the Patriarch Nikephoros I (806-815), had no resolution, so Leo was convinced that his policy was correct and had the icon of the Chalke gate, which Leo III is fictitiously claimed to have removed once before, replaced with a cross. In 815 the revival of iconoclasm was rendered official by a Synod held in the Hagia Sophia. After the death of Leo V, Michael II the Amorian (820-829) succeeded him. In a letter to the Carolingian emperor Louis the Pious, in 824, Michael lamented the appearance of image veneration in the church and such practices as making icons baptismal godfathers to infants. He confirmed the decrees of the Iconoclast Council of 754. Michael was succeeded by his son, Theophilus, who died leaving his wife Theodora the Armenian or the Blessed regent for his minor heir, Michael III the Drunkard (842-867). Albeit nearly all bishops of the empire had been forced to profess Iconoclasm, the Empress had considerable support and managed to restore the veneration of the Holy Icons in March 843, just fourteen months after her husband's death, putting thus an end to the second phase of Byzantine Iconoclasm. In order to counteract opposition and save the legacy of her late husband, she claimed that Theophilus had repented of Iconoclasm on his deathbed, a story that could also ensure that Theophilus's iconoclasm would not affect her son's reign in the future. Furthermore, the iconoclast Patriarch of Constantinople, John VII Grammaticus (837-843), was deposed and replaced with the iconophile Methodios I (843-847). The entire process was conducted in relative peace, though the Patriarch at first refused to leave his residence and showed wounds on his stomach that he claimed had been inflicted by imperial guards. Soon after becoming Patriarch, Methodios had nearly every bishop in the empire deposed due to their opposition to the Second Council of Nicaea. On 11 March 843, the restoration of the icons was celebrated in a grand procession in the Hagia Sophia. The day of Theodora's assembly and restoration of the Holy Icons has been celebrated ever since as the Feast of Orthodoxy.

Date Range: 814 CE - 823 CE

Region: The Eastern Byzantine Empire

Region tags: Asia Minor, Eastern Mediterranean, Levant, Greece, Mediterranean Coast, Eastern Europe, Anatolia, Byzantium

The Eastern Byzantine Empire c. 400 CE.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Gerhart B. Ladner. The Concept of the Image in the Greek Fathers and the Byzantine Iconoclastic Controversy. *Dumbarton Oaks Papers*. Vol. 7, (1953), pp. 1-34.

– Source 2: Brubaker, L.; Haldon, J. (2001). Byzantium in the Iconoclast Era, c. 680-850: the sources: an annotated survey. *Birmingham Byzantine and Ottoman Studies*. Vol. 7. Aldershot: Ashgate. ISBN 978-0-754-60418-1.

– Source 3: Brubaker, L.; Haldon, J. (2011). Byzantium in the Iconoclast Era, c. 680-850: A History. Cambridge University Press. ISBN 978-0-521-43093-7.

Reference: Pratsch, Thomas . Theodoros Studites (759-826)-zwischen Dogma Und Pragma: Der Abt Des Studiosklosters in Konstantinopel Im Spannungsfeld Von Patriarch, Kaiser Und Eigenem Anspruch. *Berliner Byzantinistische Studien*. Bern: Peter Lang, 1998.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/event/Iconoclastic-Controversy>

– Source 1 Description: Iconoclastic Controversy-

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.worldhistory.org/article/1161/byzantine-icons/>

– Source 2 Description: Byzantine Icons

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.schmemann.org/byhim/byzantiumiconoclasm.html>

– Source 3 Description: Byzantium, Iconoclasm and the Monks

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/source/johndam-icons.asp>

– Source 1 Description: John of Damascus: In Defense of Icons

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.ccel.org/ccel/schaff/npnf214.i.html>

– Source 2 Description: The Seven Ecumenical Councils. Their Canons and Dogmatic Decrees, Together with the Canons of All the Local Synods which have Received Ecumenical Acceptance

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The system for assigning religious affiliation was pretty straightforward: whether one accepted the worship of the Holy Icons or not.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:

– Yes

Notes: In relation to the first period, however, during which bloody conflicts took place, the second period is generally characterized as calmer and more peaceful, regarding the way and the means that the iconoclastic views were enforced.

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:

– Yes

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: However, not strictly, in the sense of a moral police. Observance was more focused on whether the faithful were in possession of icons and was mainly enforced by local bishops, who, of course, had been chosen for their iconoclastic positions

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Apostasy means worshipping or not worshipping the holy Icons. Therefore, anyone of the faithful who worshipped or refused to worship the Holy Icons was automatically considered as an apostate from one party or the other.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Both parties, iconophiles and iconoclasts had their leaders. As for the first, the iconophiles, Patriarch Nikephoros I and the Empress Theodora, Theodore of Stoudios, as well as the Patriarch Methodios I can be considered as the leaders of the iconophile party. As for the iconoclasts, the Emperor Leo V, his successor Michael II and his successor and only son Theophilos, as well as the Patriarchs Theodotos I Kassiteras, John VII Grammaticus, are considered to be the leaders of the iconoclasts.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: Technically not, but in essence yes, if hierarchy is understood as the value of the offices each held within the Empire, and not as an independent authority, hierarchically structured.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– No

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: The correct answer is yes and no, on the one hand. On the other, it must be clarified what is meant by the term iconography. In general, the iconoclasts were not against iconography per se, but against religious iconography, i.e. the depiction of the divine nature of Jesus Christ. For example, a large mosaic of a church council in the Imperial Palace was replaced by lively secular scenes, and there was no issue with imagery per se. The plain Iconoclastic cross that replaced a figurative image in the apse of St Irene's is itself an almost unique survival. For the iconophilic religious sites, it was normal to depict Jesus or the Saints. However, many of such compositions do not survive, since the fiery iconoclastic period has drastically reduced the number of survivals of Byzantine art from before the period, especially large religious mosaics, which are now almost exclusively found in Italy and Saint Catherine's Monastery in Egypt.

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: Not exactly, It should be noted however that a symbolic action taken to mark the restoration of the Holy Icons was the desecration of the tomb of the Emperor and champion of iconoclasm Constantine V. His remains were removed from his tomb in the Church of the Holy Apostles and burned, with the ashes scattered so that no site would ever be associated with his burial. His tomb in the Church of the Holy Apostles was replaced with the tomb of Empress Irene, with her remains being transferred from her previous resting place on the island of Prinkipos (today Büyükada), finally reuniting her remains with those of her husband and placing her alongside the other rulers of the empire. It is possible that Theodora admired Irene on account of her being a previous female ruler as well as a previous restorer of the icons. Irene's grave would in later years often be commemorated as the resting place of an iconophile hero.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: For both parties, iconoclasts and iconophiles, the hierarchy of the divine beings remains the same. They all worshipped the Holy Trinity, the Mother of God and the Saints. However, they rejected the fact that the divinity of such supernatural beings, particularly for Jesus Christ, could not be represented or depicted through an image (i.e. an Icon). They therefore held that any image of Jesus must be able to represent both his divine and human nature. The first was impossible, since the divine nature could ever be seen nor encompassed. For the latter, it was possible, however, making an Icon of

Jesus Christ means that one is separating his human and divine natures, since only the human can be depicted. On the contrary, iconophiles asserted that the biblical commandment forbidding images of God had been superseded by the incarnation of Jesus Christ, who is in fact, God incarnated in visible matter. Therefore, they were not depicting the invisible God, but God as He appeared in the flesh.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: Technically not. Iconoclasts and iconophiles were both Orthodox Christians, therefore they shared the same eschatological views, posited by the Bible and the Fathers of the Church.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Obedience to social norms depended on the party to which one belonged. This means that for an iconophile during the period in question, worshipping the Holy Icons was not only a sign of orthodoxy and orthopraxy, but also of social correctness, since he/she was considered as aligned with the tradition of the Church. This was based on the assertion that idols depicted persons without substance or reality, while the Holy Icons depicted real persons, that is the incarnated Jesus Christ, or other real people who had lived in the past (the Saints, the martyrs etc.) and formed the tradition. For the iconoclasts, on the other hand, the use for religious purposes was viewed as an inappropriate innovation in the Church, and a return to pagan practice, which apparently was condemned both religiously and socially.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The moral code of both iconophiles and iconoclasts was common. Apparently, certain aspects may have been somewhat different, depending on the attitude towards the veneration or not of the Holy Icons. However, the basic virtues of Christianity remained common to both.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:
– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:
– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:
– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:
– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):
– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:
– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:
– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: For example, the iconoclast Patriarch of Constantinople John VII was deposed and sent to exile in a monastery by the Bosphorus.

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: There is the case with the deposed Patriarch of Constantinople John VII, whom the Empress Theodora had him whipped two hundred times. although she originally wanted to blind him.

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s)

other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The institutionalized military in question is the Byzantine military.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

- Pastoralism
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Field doesn't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Cormack, Robin. *Writing in Gold, Byzantine Society and Its Icons*. London: George Philip, 1985.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Gwynn, David. "From Iconoclasm to Arianism. The Construction of Christian Tradition in the Iconoclast Controversy". *Greek, Roman, and Byzantine Studies* 47 (2007): 226–51.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Cormack, Robin. "Art and Iconoclasm". In *The Oxford Handbook of Byzantine Studies*. Oxford Handbooks. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2009.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Cormack, Robin. *The Byzantine Eye: Studies in Art and Patronage*. Variorum Collected Studies Series / 296. London: Variorum, 1989.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Cormack, Robin. "Looking for Iconophobia and Iconoclasm in Late Antiquity and Byzantium". In *Iconoclasm and Text Destruction in the Ancient Near East and Beyond*, 471–84. Chicago: The Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, 2012.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Cormack, Robin. "Painting After Iconoclasm". In *Iconoclasm. Papers Given at the Ninth Spring Symposium of Byzantine Studies, University of Birmingham, March 1975*, 147–63. Birmingham: University of Birmingham, 1977.
<https://www.fulcrum.org/concern/monographs/vq27zn57c>.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Garland, Lynda. "Theodora, Restorer of Orthodoxy". In *Byzantine Empresses: Women and Power in Byzantium AD 527–1204.*, 95–108. London: Routledge, 1999.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Treadgold, Warren . *A History of the Byzantine State and Society.* Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1997.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Karagianni, Alexandra. "Female Monarchs in the Medieval Byzantine Court: Prejudice, Disbelief and Calumnies". In *Queenship in the Mediterranean: Negotiating the Role of the Queen in the Medieval and Early Modern Eras*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2013.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Herrin, Judith. *Women in Purple: Rulers of Medieval Byzantium*. London: Phoenix Press, 2002.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Gero, Stephen . *Byzantine Iconoclasm During the Reign of Constantine V, with Particular Attention to the Oriental Sources*. Leuven: Peeters, 1977.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Humphreys, Mike . *A Companion to Byzantine Iconoclasm*. Brill's Companions to the Christian Tradition. Leiden, Boston: Brill, 2021.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Domínguez, Óscar Prieto . *Literary Circles in Byzantine Iconoclasm: Patrons, Politics and Saints*. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, 2021.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Carnes, Natalie. *Image and Presence: A Christological Reflection on Iconoclasm and Iconophilia*. Encountering Traditions. Stanford;California: Stanford University Press, 2018.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Shevchenko, Ihor . "Hagiography of the Iconoclast Period". In *Iconoclasm*. Birmingham: University of Birmingham, 1977.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Auzépy, Marie-France . "L'analyse Littéraire Et L'historien: L'exemple Des Vies De Saints Iconoclastes". *Byzantinoslavica* 53 (1992): 57-67.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Brubaker, Leslie , and John Haldon. *Byzantium in the Iconoclast Era, C. 680-850: A History*. Cambridge : Cambridge University Press, n.d..

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Besançon, Alain . *The Forbidden Image: An Intellectual History of Iconoclasm*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2000.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, McClanan, Anne , Jeffrey Johnson, and Jeff Johnson. *Negating the Image: Case Studies in Iconoclasm*. Aldershot: Ashgate, 2005.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Stapleton, Rachel , and Antonio Viselli, eds.. *Iconoclasm: The Breaking and Making of Images*. Edited by Rachel Stapleton and Antonio Viselli. Montreal: McGill-Queen's University Press, 2019.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Codoñer, Juan Signes . *The Emperor Theophilos and the East. Court and Frontier in Byzantium During the Last Phase of Iconoclasm*. Birmingham Byzantine and Ottoman Studies (book 13). Farnham: Routledge, 2014.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Barber, Charles . *Figure and Likeness: On the Limits of Representation in Byzantine Iconoclasm*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2002.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Brubaker, Leslie. *Inventing Byzantine Iconoclasm*. Studies in Early Medieval History. London: Bristol Classical Press, 2012.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, von Grunebaum, Gustave. "Byzantine Iconoclasm and the Influence of the Islamic Environment". *History of Religions* 2, no. 1 (1962): 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1062034>.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Kitzinger, Ernst . "The Cult of Images in the Age Before Iconoclasm". *Dumbarton Oaks Papers* 8 (1954): 83-150. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1291064> .

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Baynes, Norman . "The Icons Before Iconoclasm". *The Harvard Theological Review* 44, no. 2 (1951): 93-106. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1508902>.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Gero, Stephen. "Byzantine Iconoclasm and Monachomachy". *The Journal of Ecclesiastical History* 28, no. 3 (1977): 241 248. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0022046900041439>.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Barber, Charles . "From Transformation to Desire: Art and Worship After Byzantine Iconoclasm". *The Art Bulletin* 75, no. 1 (1993): 7-16. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3045929> .

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Smith, Jason Domonick. John Grammatikos: An Oblique History of a Damned Patriarch (phd Thesis). Sacramento: California State University, 2010. <https://csu-csus.esploro.exlibrisgroup.com/esploro/outputs/graduate/John-Grammatikos-an-oblique-history-of/99257831069501671>.

Reference: The second phase of the Iconoclastic Controversy, Speck, Paul . Theodoros Studites. Jamben Auf Verschiedene Gegenstände. Berlin: De Gruyter, 1968.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Source 1: Gerhart B. Ladner. The Concept of the Image in the Greek Fathers and the Byzantine Iconoclastic Controversy. *Dumbarton Oaks Papers*. Vol. 7, (1953), pp. 1-34., Source 2: Brubaker, L.; Haldon, J. (2001). *Byzantium in the Iconoclast Era, c. 680-850: the sources: an annotated survey*. Birmingham Byzantine and Ottoman Studies. Vol. 7. Aldershot: Ashgate. ISBN 978-0-754-60418-1., Source 3: Brubaker, L.; Haldon, J. (2011). *Byzantium in the Iconoclast Era, c. 680-850: A History*. Cambridge University Press. ISBN 978-0-521-43093-7., Pratsch, Thomas . *Theodoros Studites (759-826)-zwischen Dogma Und Pragma: Der Abt Des Studiosklosters in Konstantinopel Im Spannungsfeld Von Patriarch, Kaiser Und Eigenem Anspruch*. Berliner Byzantinistische Studien. Bern: Peter Lang, 1998.